

Agentic-AI pipeline architecture for Deep Farm project

(application to a pilot digital rice farm in Madagascar)

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1. Abstract

In Madagascar, an agriculture-based country where 80% of the population lives in rural areas and 75% are farmers, rice cultivation is the primary activity—both for subsistence and commercial purposes. Agriculture lies at the heart of the Malagasy economy, with rice farming being a cornerstone of the nation’s food security. Rice accounts for 12% of the national GDP and 43% of agricultural added value. Yet the country faces a paradox: once self-sufficient, Madagascar now needs to import rice to meet domestic consumption due to low yields and outdated farming practices.

Persistent challenges include recurring diseases, lack of accessible information on treatment methods, and difficulties in real-time monitoring of fields. According to [7], over 30% of rice yield losses in Sub-Saharan Africa are due to diseases and environmental stress, exacerbated by the lack of technological infrastructure. Moreover, hundreds of locally produced reports and scientific documents remain underutilized—either inaccessible or too complex for farmers to understand.

The DEEP RICE project, part of the broader Erasmus+ Deep Farm program (ERASMUS-EDU-2023-CBHE-STRAND-2, Project number: 101128032), aims to leverage digital tools—particularly artificial intelligence—and data generated by connected objects (IoT) such as sensors and drones, to improve production, optimize water use, detect and prevent disease, and monitor crop maturity.

AI and digital technologies represent a tremendous opportunity to enhance agricultural production in an eco-responsible manner (9), while also fostering the creation of open “**digital commons**” (DATA COMMONS) to support the development of AI applications (10).

Tomorrow, every farmer could carry a “digital tutor” in their pocket—on a smartphone—(1)(2) that provides access to both public and private data. This AI application will interface with large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT, Mistral, and DeepSeek (3). A Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) system (4) will act as a bridge between private vectorized data and public data accessed through the LLM, providing a unified representation aligned with LLM capabilities.

AI application development is facing an important disruptive approach with AGENTIC AI ((6), (11), (12) et (13) to bridge the gap between predictive AI and generative AI.

An AI agent is an **autonomous AI application**. Open-source platforms such as LangChain (6) provide a complete value chain for building multi-agent systems—from the embedding of internal (and often multimodal) data such as text, images, videos, or audio, to the development and orchestration of multiple AI agents on multiple LLM (Large language models) (3) .

This digital farm tutor is thus an AI agent capable of integrating historical private datasets and the empirical knowledge passed down by farmers through generations—a tacit heritage often overlooked by modern agricultural systems.

In this article, we present the dual AI architecture proposed within the DEEP RICE (and DEEP FARM) frameworks, which integrates both predictive AI and generative AI:

- A classic pipeline architecture currently being implemented in pilot farms of the project (featuring machine learning methods for disease detection and water optimization);
- A new AGENTIC-AI pipeline architecture introduced in this article, based on large language models, RAG systems (5).

This paper outlines an innovative architecture **to develop virtual tutoring with AI AGENTS** where predictive AI (image diagnostics, sensor data analysis) and generative AI (RAG systems with LLMs) work together to provide personalized support to rice farmers in the form of a digital AI tutor.

IOT (Internet of things) in DEEP FARM include low cost SENSORS and DRONES (with classical multipectral images) to aim at family farming.

Within the new European project called FRUCTHOR starting in 2025 at ESTIA, we will implement a digital PILOT farm in the Basque Wine country (DEEP IROULEGUY project) using an extra autonomous solar robot from MIALTECH, a French start up (<https://www.mialtech.com/>) to enrich the Deep Farm IOT platform

2. The DEEP RICE Project

DEEP RICE is a subproject of the DEEP FARM program, funded by the European Union through Erasmus+, and coordinated by ESTIA (École Supérieure des Technologies Industrielles Avancées) in France – www.estia.fr. This program aims to promote the emergence of sustainable digital agriculture through the use of DATA and artificial intelligence.

DEEP RICE focuses specifically on rice cultivation in Madagascar, relying on a local and international ecosystem of stakeholders to design an intelligent, **multi-agent AI architecture** adapted to local conditions.

The project is implemented in Madagascar by a consortium composed of:

- IT University (ITU) in charge of the technological and AI components with eBIHAR master students from ESTIA);
- UNIVA University contributing agronomic expertise;
- ANAE organization, responsible for the implementation of the pilot farm and interaction with farmers on the ground.

The main objectives of the project are:

- To strengthen rice productivity, optimize water usage, detect/prevent diseases, and manage climate-related crises through digital tools;

- To valorize local know-how, often scattered in scientific reports or in the tacit knowledge of farmers, by creating a DATA COMMONS for rice cultivation (aggregating both internal and external rice-related data sets and knowledge);
- To offer personalized digital support via a mobile AI application accessible to farmers: the *digital farm Tutor*.

One of DEEP RICE's key strengths lies in its ability to combine advanced technologies (LLMs, IoT, computer vision, geodata) with a deep understanding of local knowledge and socio-agricultural context. The close cooperation between computer scientists, agronomists, and end-users enables the development of solutions that are genuinely useful, robust, and transferable to other agricultural regions.

3. IoT Components and Predictive AI Data: Sensors, Images, and Detection

The DEEP RICE project integrates several predictive AI technologies to provide rice farmers with accurate and contextualized diagnostics. These components form the first layer of intelligence in the system, built on real-time field data analysis.

IOT components producing real-time DATA are sensors (time-series DATA) and drones (image data)

- Disease Prediction from Images

A deep learning model based on ResNet-50 (https://pytorch.org/hub/pytorch_vision_resnet/) was trained on more than 7,500 annotated images from a Kaggle dataset, divided into five classes (four diseases: Blast, Brown Spot, Sheath Blight, Leaf Smut, and one healthy class). Thanks to transfer learning, the model achieved an accuracy of **97.53%**, although some overfitting remains in specific classes.

This model is embedded in a mobile application that allows farmers to take photos of their rice plants and receive a real-time diagnosis.

Drone Image Analysis

Pipeline for Rice Field Monitoring

Drone-based disease detection pipeline

Infrastructure DEEP RICE

Deep Rice Infrastructure

4. Multi-Agent AI Architecture (AGENTIC AI)

The technological core of the DEEP RICE project lies in an architecture of intelligent, specialized agents, capable of collaborating to analyze, interpret, and present agricultural information in an actionable way for users—particularly farmers and researchers.

Our fundamental incremental idea is to associate an agent with every IOT DATA FLOW.

This architecture relies on two complementary pillars :

- Predictive AI to interpret quantitative data from sensors and images;
- Generative AI enhanced by retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) to produce context-rich reasoning based on internal documents and field observations.

● Why a Multi-Agent AI Architecture?

The complexity and multimodality of agricultural data—stemming from IoT devices, images, human observations, and documents—requires a modular and specialized architecture. This needs standardized representations (thru embedding/vectorization) that are compatible with LLMs and enable long-term MEMORY.

Moreover, current large language models are limited by token constraints (text units used in generative AI). Attempting to process all sources with a single agent increases the risk of hallucinations or imprecise answers.

A multi-agent approach offers several advantages:

1. Assigns specific roles to different types of data or AI processes,
2. Facilitates scalability and system evolution,
3. Improves maintenance, monitoring, and progressive skill development of each agent,
4. Enhances transparency and traceability of the reasoning process for end-users,
5. Overcomes LLM limitations by distributing responsibilities among specialized agents,
6. Enables intelligent orchestration of responses through a coordinator agent.

We chose LangChain (6) for vectorization, agent development, and orchestration.

● Global Architecture

The system is built upon a multi-agent architecture with the following roles:

1. **Time Series Agent:** Collects physical field data (temperature, humidity, rainfall, pH, water level, NPK, etc.) from IoT sensors and historical CSV files. These are timestamped, geolocated, and linked to specific plots. It can detect anomalies or temporal correlations based on embedded agronomic rules or documents.
2. **Image Agent:** Encodes images (e.g., rice leaves or drone views) into vectors and performs similarity searches in a vector image database. It can retrieve similar disease-related images and contextualize them.
3. **Document Agent:** Manages all document sources (PDFs, reports, articles, OCR-extracted texts). It extracts, chunks, vectorizes, and indexes these texts in a vector database.
4. **Coordinator Agent:** Centralizes communication, orchestrates logic, resolves conflicts, and prioritizes between data sources. It decides which agents to query for a given user request and merges their responses into a coherent, enriched output.

- Vectorization and Generation Pipeline (Technical Overview)

The technical process for building the RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation) system within a multi-agent architecture involves the following steps:

1. **Extraction** : Content is extracted from various sources (PDFs, CSVs, OCR images, etc.).
2. **Chunking** : Texts are segmented into chunks of 400 to 600 tokens (with overlap) to preserve contextual continuity.
3. **Embedding** : Each chunk is transformed into a dense vector using an encoder such as all-mpnet-base-v2 from SentenceTransformers., <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-mpnet-base-v2>
4. **Vector Storage** : Vectors are stored in a vector database such as PostgreSQL with pgvector or Chroma DB.
5. **Vector Search**: When a user submits a query, the question is embedded and compared to stored vectors using **cosine similarity** (which measures the angle between vectors in n-dimensional space) or <-> PostgreSQL)
6. **Filtering and Selection**: The most relevant chunks are selected using either threshold filtering or stochastic top-k sampling.
7. **Génération** :A dynamic prompt is generated (with instructions based on document type) and sent to an LLM (such as DeepSeek, Mistral, or a GPT-like model) for response generation.

Generative AI and Agentic AI : Data Ingestion Pipeline

Pipeline: from multi-source data to the vector database

- Multi-Agent Query Processing Pipeline

When a user submits a query, the multi-agent system processes it through the following steps :

1. **Query Reception**: The **Coordinator Agent** receives the user's request.

2. **Semantic Analysis:** It analyzes the query's semantics to identify the relevant data sources (e.g., real-time sensor data, images, documents).
3. **Delegation to Specialized Agents:** The coordinator dispatches the request to one or more specialized agents (Time Series, Image, Document, etc.).
4. **Local Processing:** Each agent independently processes the query within its scope and returns an intermediate result (e.g., explanation, prediction, contextual information).
5. **Aggregation and Fusion:** The Coordinator Agent gathers and merges all intermediate results to formulate a unified response.
6. **Final Generation:** If necessary, a prompt is generated and sent to an LLM via the RAG Agent, which reformulates or enriches the response using textual knowledge.

Generative AI and Agentic AI : Request Flow & Processing

Pipeline for processing a multi-agent query

Multi-Agent Scenario Example

A user asks via the application:

"What is the impact of high humidity on rice diseases in my plot?"

The system combines the following:

- **Recent sensor data** from the **Time Series Agent** (humidity levels in the user's plot);
- A **scientific summary** from the **Document Agent** regarding humidity-related diseases;
- **Historical analysis** from CSV datasets;
- And finally, a **synthetic response** generated by the **RAG Agent**.

This allows for **cross-referenced, contextual reasoning**, enriched by **local knowledge**, which is the core of the DEEP RICE architecture.

Final Augmented Prompt Sent to the LLM

```
## Contexte :  
- Tu es un agent numérique spécialisé en agriculture du riz.  
- Utilise les informations suivantes pour répondre :  
  
{context}  
  
## Question :  
- question de l'utilisateur :  
...  
  
{query}  
...  
  
Contraintes :  
- Réponds de façon simple et explique bien les choses  
- Tu dois parler la langue de l'utilisateur  
- Réponds que tu n'est pas capable de répondre à cette question si au  
moins l'un de ces conditions est satisfait  
+ le contexte ne suffit pas à répondre la question  
+ l'utilisateur parle de chose en dehors de l'agriculture sauf si c'est une  
salutation ou qui ne parle pas de sujet tres spécifique  
+ par contre c'est ok sur le sujet de deep farm  
Réponse :
```

LLM Prompt Template

```
### PDF section  
- voici les informations sur les pdf enregistrées.  
- Il sont généralement des rapport ou article scientifique.  
- il faut plus considéré ces informations par rapport aux autres.  
...  
{content}  
...  
### FIN PDF section
```

LLM Prompt Template for PDF


```
### CSV section  
- ces donnés sont issues de fichier CSV  
- il faut les prendre en compte pour :  
+ faire des estimation  
+ prédire quelque chose en se basant sur les données fournit par ces csv  
...  
{content}  
...  
### fin CSV section
```

LLM Prompt Template for CSV

Prompts sent to the LLM

7. Experimental Deep Rice Farm in Madagascar

To experiment with, test, and validate the proposed architecture, a **pilot farm** has been established in **Savainakely, Bongatsara**, on the southern outskirts of Madagascar's capital, **Antananarivo**.

This 2-hectare agricultural site serves as the **main testing ground** for the DEEP RICE project.

- Deployed Infrastructure

Several **smart stations** have been installed on the farm. Each station consists of:

1. An **Arduino Mega microcontroller** acting as the central hub;
2. An **ESP-01S module** for communication with a remote server via Wi-Fi;
3. A suite of agricultural sensors, including:
 - a. **Air temperature and humidity sensor (DHT22)**
 - b. **Water level sensor (YB-2J-F)**
 - c. **Rain gauge** (tipping bucket type)
 - d. **Soil pH sensor**
 - e. **NPK sensor** for nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium levels

Each station is **solar-powered**, making the solution viable even in remote rural areas.

Data is transmitted periodically through a **local network** to a **Raspberry Pi**, which acts as a hub.

From there, the data is sent to a **central server**.

- Connection with Agricultural Plots

The land has been divided into distinct **agricultural plots**, and each smart station is **geolocated** and linked to the plot it monitors. This enables:

- **Real-time monitoring** of agro-environmental variables;
- **Structured storage** in a **spatio-temporal database**;
- **Interactive map visualization** in the mobile application.

Figure 12: Overview of the 2-hectare pilot site

Conclusion : The multi-agent architecture proposed in DEEP RICE represents the digital future of pilot farm infrastructure within the DEEP FARM framework.

By combining predictive and generative AI, it offers a robust and context-aware system to provide DIGITAL CUSTOMIZED TUTORING for rice farmers, built around real-time data, scientific knowledge, and local know-how.

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